

Behavioural Response of *Rasbora daniconius* Exposed to Two Different Concentrations of Captan

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Abstract

In the present study two different concentrations, 0.50mg/L and 1.5mg/L of the fungicide captan were evaluated with respect to behavioural responses under experimental condition to the adult fishes *Rasbora daniconius*. The behavioural changes occur when fishes were exposed to two different concentrations of 0.50mg/L and 1.5mg/L of captan. The exposed fishes shows abnormal behaviour depending on the dose of the captan and duration of exposure. The fishes exposed to 0.50 mg/L of captan shows minor behavioural signs of restlessness and jumping movement after addition of the captan. Less mucous secretion, less fecal matter deposition and as good as normal feeding also occur during this exposure. The intensity of behavioural changes increased with increasing concentration and time exposure. The fishes exposed to 1.5 mg/L captan exhibited signs of restlessness, erratic swimming and excess mucous secretion. Convulsion,rapid opercular movement, leaping and sluggish movement. The distinct changes occur was excess fecal matter deposition and reduced feeding, when fishes exposed to 96hr duration to captan.

KEY WORDS- Behavioural response, *Rasbora daniconius*, Two different concentration, Captan.

Introduction

Behavioural toxicology deals with the effects of different chemicals or poisons on the behavioural patterns of organisms due to acute or sub-acute toxicity. Whenever an organism comes into the contact with a chemical or poison, it shows some kind of reaction which will be manifested in its changed behaviour patterns, which is not seen in its normal behaviour. Such altered behavioural pattern of organisms under the influence of some poison or chemical are studied in the behavioural toxicology. Behavioural response in an organism is a indicator of their surrounding environmental

condition. The behavioural toxicology is a type of biological study which find out the environmental conditions by analysing behavioural response of species. Behaviour of aquatic animals like fishes is good indicator of water quality. Behaviour of an animal is an indicator of their physical as well as biochemical condition.

Over use of pesticides enters into the water bodies by several ways like agricultural runoff and industrial effluents form. Pesticides enters into water bodies and harms the aquatic organisms. The aquatic organisms are exposed to different types of pesticides through several pathways such as through skin, gills and oral cavity.

Captan is one of the fungicides belongs to pthalmid family. It is used to control diseases in many vegetables and fruits. It acts on fungus and reacts with sulfhydryl group and it reduces fungal spore germination, growth and oxygen uptake (Owens and Novotny 1959). Captan is non-volatile substance and it rapidly hydrolyses in water, so it is used in agricultural field to kill fungal born diseases. Even applied in small agricultural areas, captan enters into water bodies by several ways. It causes water pollution and harm the aquatic animals.

Behavioural response in fishes is an indicator of their surrounding environmental condition. The behavioural changes are the obvious of the motivational, biochemical, physiological and environmental influence state of the fishes. Many workers work on behavioural changes among different species of fishes treated with different pesticides. Number of workers work on the fresh water fish *Rasbora daniconius* and treated it with different pesticides and reported the behavioural changes in this fish (Sarkar and Saha 2018; Pathan et.al; 2009; Bhandare et. al;2011; Pandey et.al; 2011; Kaur and Dua 2012; Jacquin et.al;2020)

Material and methods

The fresh water fishes *Rasbora daniconius* were collected from local fresh water bodies from Tasgaon and Palus tahsils of Sangli district (M.S). The live fishes were brought to the laboratory and were acclimatized in laboratory condition in glass aquaria for 15 days before experiment. During acclimatization fishes were fed with fish food which is available in market in pouch. The fishes used for the study having mean length 8.2 ± 0.5 cm and mean weight 5.0 ± 0.3 gm. The toxicant used for the experiment was captan which is available in agrochemical shop of the local market.

Physico-chemical parameters of water of both aquaria having water without captan and water with captan were analysed by standard methods of APHA, AWWA and WPCF (1985) and Trivedy, Goel and Bhave (1985).

Physicochemical parameters analysed were pH, Electrical conductivity (EC), Total dissolved solids(TDS), Total hardness, Carbonates (CO_3^{2-}), Bicarbonates(HCO_3^-), Calcium (Ca^{++}), Magnesium(Mg),Sodium(Na), Pottassium (K), Chlorides (Cl^-), Phosphate (PO_4), Sulphate (SO_4^-), Nitrate (NO_3), Dissolved Oxygen (DO_2) and free CO_2 .

The water in test aquaria was changed every 24hrs. For experimentation laboratory acclimatized fishes were exposed to two different concentrations such as 0.5 mg/L and 1.5mg/L of captan. A batch of 10 fishes was treated with 0.5 mg/l of captan and another batch of 10 fishes was treated with 1.5 mg/L of captan. A batch of 10 fishes was also maintained along with experimental fishes as control group. The changes in behaviour of *Rasbora daniconius* exposed to two different concentrations of captan were observed during the experimentation.

Results

The fishes exposed to two different concentrations 0.5 mg/L of captan and 1.5 mg/L of captan shows changes in general behaviour and mortality differently.

The fishes exposed to 0.5 mg/L of captan for 24 hrs,48hrs,72 hrs and 96 hrs show remarkable behavioural changes in which fishes shows jumping after addition of the captan. This jumping movement carried upto an hrs and then fishes becomes calm and quiet and behave normally. Other changes occur were less mucous secretion and less fecal matter deposition. The feeding behaviour occur was normal. The fishes exposed to 1.5 mg/L of captan for 24hrs,48hrs ,72 hrs and 96 hrs shows remarkable changes in general behaviour and mortality. The behavioural changes reported were erratic swimming,convulsion,rapid opercular movement, leaping, mucous secretion, sluggish movement, reduced feeding behaviour and excess fecal matter deposition.

The control group fishes swim normally throughout the tank but the fishes treated with 1.5 mg/L captan exhibited erratic swimming.

The irregular movement of the body also reported when treated with 1.5 mg/L captan. This movement is caused by involuntary contraction of muscles.

The control group fishes shows normal opercular movement but the fishes treated with 1.5 mg/L captan exhibit rapid opercular movement. The fishes struggled for breathing and take atmospheric air and try to avoid toxic medium.

The fishes treated with 1.5 mg/L captan exhibit leaping. Most of the time fishes leap out from the tank. Fishes shows jerky movement after treated with captan.

The fishes treated with both 0.5 mg/L captan and 1.5 mg/L captan were exhibited thick mucous covering over the body surface.

The fishes treated with 1.5 mg/L captan shows sluggish movement at the end of acute treatment.

Control group fishes exhibit normal food consumption but the experimental fishes treated with 1.5 mg/L captan shows reduced feeding behaviour.

The fishes treated with 1.5 mg/L captan shows deposition of excess fecal matter on next day as compared to fishes treated with 0.5mg/L captan.

Physico chemical parameters after captan treatment shows increased values were Electrical conductivity (EC) ,Total dissolved solids(TDS), Bicarbonates (HCO_3^-), Magnesium (Mg), Sodium (Na), Pottasium(K), Phosphate (PO_4), Sulphate (SO_4^-), Nitrate(NO_3) and Free CO_2 .

Physico chemical parameters after captan treatment shows decreased values were P^{H} , total hardness, Calcium (Ca^{++}), Chlorides (Cl^-) and Dissolved O_2 . Carbonates (CO_3^{2-}) are absent in both water sample with captan or without captan.

Sr.No	Physico-chemical parameters	Unit	Results as per analysis without captan	Results as per analysis with captan
1	PH		7.86	7.75
2	Electrical Conductivity	μmhos	0.930	1.015
3	Total Dissolved Solids(TDS)	mg/L	595	849
4	Total Hardness	mg/L	320	300
5	Carbonates (CO_3^{2-})	mg/L	Ab	Ab
6	Bicarbonates (HCO_3^-)	mg/L	195.2	244
7	Calcium (Ca)	mg/L	96	84
8	Magnesium (Mg)	mg/L	19.2	21.6
9	Sodium (Na)	mg/L	92.1	111.7
10	Potassium (K)	mg/L	0.4	1.2
11	Chlorides (Cl^-)	mg/L	120.7	106.5
12	Phosphate (PO_4)	mg/L	0.40	0.96
13	Sulphate(SO_4^-)	mg/L	44	49

14	Nitrate (NO ₃)	mg/L	30.03	34.79
15	Dissolved Oxygen (DO ₂)	mg/L	8.48	6.6
16	Free carbon dioxide (Free CO ₂)	mg/L	6.06	19.8

Table: Comparison of physico-chemical parameters of water without captan and with captan.

Discussion

According to Bhandare et.al (2011),fishes exposed to lethal concentration of Rogor showed opercular movement which could be due to clearance of the accumulated mucus debris in the gill region for proper breathing. The fishes were avoiding toxic water with fast swimming and jumping faster.

When Indian carp, *Labeo rohita* was exposed to municipal waste water, it occupied the water surface in the first three highest concentrations mid to upstream column in fourth and confined to the bottom in case of lowest concentration and control. With an increase in exposure duration, the fishes in different concentrations occupied the bottom of tank.

Binsha and Binitha (2014) studied the behavioural changes of *Cyprinus carpio*. When they were exposed to fungicide tebuconazole the breath rate of fishes becomes very high and swimming activity increases. Singh and Narain (1982) exposed *Cyprinus carpio* to dimethoate and observed erratic swimming, decreased rate of opercular movement, increased mucus secretion and inability to maintain normal posture in fishes.

Patnaik and Patra (2006) concluded that fish become restless when they come in contact with pesticide and become hyperactive.

Nimai Saha et.al (2006) studied toxic effect of mancozeb to *Oreochromis mossambicus* and found excess mucous secretion on all over body.

Conclusion

The present study may provide additional data on the toxicity of captan fungicide which was harmful to fresh water fish *Rasbora daniconius*.Its discharge into water bodies will be hazardous to aquatic ecosystem in many ways. It was concluded by the study of physico-chemical parameters.

The physico-chemical parameters of water after treatment shows increasing and decreasing values as compared with the physico-chemical parameters of normal water. Fish exposed to different concentrations of captan shows behavioural changes.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declared that they have no conflicts of interest.

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